

Marketing Mixed Strategy on Increasing Amount of Tenant: Case Study in Focal Point Medan

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ABSTRACT

Mall property business is one of the promising prospects in Indonesia. This is indicated by the mushrooming number of malls in Indonesia as many as 708 units, while specifically in the city of Medan recorded as many as 15 units of malls or shopping centers that exist. There is a uniqueness along the Ringroad Street, Medan, where there are 3 (three) malls namely Medan Focal Point, Ringroad City Walk and Manhattan Times Square. However, among the three malls, Medan Focal Point is experiencing stagnation in terms of visitors and also the number of tenants. The number of tenants in Medan Focal Points from 2014 to 2019 decreased. This is due to among other things the comfort of the building, the location of parking, communication with management, the lack of promotion which in turn causes the number of visitors to decrease. The results showed simultaneously, there was a positive and significant influence of the 7P marketing mix on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point. While partially only two variables namely "Promotion" and "Process" which have a positive and significant effect on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point. While 5 (five) other variables (Product, Price, Place, Physical Evidence, and People) do not have a partial correlation with the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point. Whereas strategic advice is addressed to Medan Focal Point management so that managers pay attention and focus on the management of their promotions and processes, including the procurement of events to increase public knowledge of Medan Focal Points and interact with tenants, listen to their aspirations and facilitate administration and others so that tenants feel fulfilled what is their complaint.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Physical Evidence, People, Process, Tenant, Space, Purchase Decision

INTRODUCTION

The development of time and the level of human growth are so fast, encouraging people to continue to meet their needs, both primary (secondary), secondary and even tertiary. Various efforts in terms of meeting these needs they get from markets or shopping places. Markets or shopping areas are also progressing, if in the past the market was an open area or space, now the market is developing into a closed area or in certain buildings. By the 1900s, many shopping centers or malls had begun to stand up. The nature of this shopping center is to collect many types of merchants (clusters) grouped (cluster) in certain areas, that is why it is said shopping is centered (center), so that buyers do not need to go to other shopping places to meet their needs. They just come to the shopping center and all their needs are met.

The shopping center in Indonesia was first present in 1963. Sarinah Plaza is the first mall in Indonesia. The mall, located in the center of Jakarta, was inaugurated in 1967 by President Soekarno. The name Sarinah was conceived by President Soekarno himself, which Sarinah was the name of President Soekarno's caregiver when he was a child. The presence of Sarinah Plaza at that time was expected to encourage the Indonesian economy which had just been freed from colonialism. Evidently, at that time Sarinah Plaza (at the

first time it was formed was still called "Convenience Stores") able to drive the economy not only in Jakarta, but in Indonesia. At that time imported luxury goods were sold there and the hunters for these luxury goods did not only come from Jakarta, but from all over Indonesia. Comes with 3 (three) floors, the first floor provides male and female equipment, electrical equipment and lighting. Then on the second floor providing textile items, convection, and children's toys. While on the third floor there are household appliances and stationery.

Furthermore, many malls have grown in Indonesia. Malls became a very promising property business not only then but now. Malls not only provide shopping centers, but also meet the lifestyle needs of urban and modern communities. Malls have become a gathering place for young people and also business people, becoming a place of entertainment, recreation, even providing learning facilities, sports, cinema and even exhibition or exhibition places (Ndungu, 2014). This is a source of income in the mall property business, which is not only from space rent, but from parking, shows, advertising (advertising), and others. This business is very promising, so it's no wonder many are wrestled by business people. In addition, the mall is also used as a "sweetener" for the apartment or office property business. Malls are considered not only as a complement, but are able to encourage the level of occupancy of apartments and / or offices, because with the presence of malls, apartments and / or offices become crowded.

It is undeniable the "life" of the mall is the number of visitors. The more crowded the visitors, the more tenants, shows and advertisements. Various attempts were made by mall developers to bring visitors. At the time of the mall construction, the developer had identified who their potential visitors were, whether middle class or upper class. Departing from here, the image of the mall is formed, whether the upper class mall or just ordinary mall. Sun Plaza in Medan

has the image of a high-end mall, so the average tenants are highly reputable merchants, such as Zara, iBox, Sogo outlets. These brands are premium brands. Unlike the Medan Fair Plaza in Medan City, where the mall is known as a shopping center for the middle class.

At present there are 708 shopping centers throughout Indonesia. The highest number is found in West Java Province with 139 shopping centers beating out of DKI Jakarta Province with 80 shopping centers. While the number of shopping centers in North Sumatra Province is 39 units (BPS, 2019). North Sumatra is one of the major provinces in Indonesia. The population level in North Sumatra is the largest outside Java. The economic development in this province is also quite promising. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (2019) noted that North Sumatra is ranked 6th as the province with the most shopping centers (malls). One of the big cities in North Sumatra, Medan City. Medan City has recorded 15 shopping center units and is included in the top 10 cities that have the most malls in Indonesia. This makes the developers of mall developers eyeing Medan City to be one of the mall development goals.

Of the many malls in Medan, there is one uniqueness in Ringroad, Medan, because along the road there are 3 (three) malls which are currently still active, namely Manhattan Times Square, Ringroad City Walks and Medan Focal Point These three malls offer interesting concepts. Manhattan Times Square is part of Manhattan Hotels, Apartments and Offices, while Ringroad City Walks is more for entertainment and Medan Focal Point Mall offers a variety of integrated minimalist shopping and entertainment concepts. Of the three malls, Medan Focal Point is the first mall located on Ringroad. At first the reason Medan Focal Point chose this location was because of its very strategic position, located in the middle to upper class housing area, namely Taman Setia Budi Indah I and II housing complex and Bukit Hijau Regency which is the most expensive

housing in Medan City. In addition, this location is also in a densely populated area, namely Sunggal, Setia Budi, Ngumban Surbakti and surrounding areas.

At the beginning of the opening in 2014, Medan Focal Point had very diverse tenants namely supermarkets, restaurants, coffee shops, cafes, book stores, homeware, karaoke and others. This mall is targeting middle class and upper urban society. Medan Focal Point was inaugurated on November 22, 2014. They were present carrying the concept of lifestyle mall that focuses on the concept of a modern lifestyle for families and young people (Medan Focal Point Management, 2019).

Citra is certainly mind-boggling in the community's evaluation of Medan Focal Points. Realizing this, Medan Focal Point management established public communication with the community, among others by organizing the promotion of the UMKM Medan City and various other events. This is of course to lure visitors and convince visitors that it is safe to visit Medan Focal Point.

Since it was officially opened in 2014, tenants at Medan Focal Point experienced fluctuations from year to year, with the highest number of tenants being in 2017, with 29 tenants with various tenors ranging from 2, 3 to 5 years.

Based on the concept of consumer behavior, repeat purchases occur due to the accumulation of experiences that consumers feel (Hawkins and Mothersbaugh, 2016). The better they feel, the greater the repetition, conversely if consumers experience unpleasant experiences not only repetition, but also have a bad image on the brand image, because consumers will preach to colleagues / other friends. The results of interviews with the management of Medan Focal Point Mal stated that in reality the current condition of Medan Focal Point has no more supermarkets since the cessation of the Macan Yaohan Supermarket due to bankruptcy since 2016. This factor certainly does more or less affect other merchants in

determining decisions whether rent or not at Medan Focal Point.

It is necessary for the management of Medan Focal Point to develop a blueprint for business development strategies to be able to increase the number of visitors which in the end will certainly increase the number of merchants who rent at Medan Focal Point. The marketing strategy that is quite widely used by various stakeholders is 4P, but in the service business this strategy is usually developed into 7P. The 7P strategy includes focus on product development, price, location, promotion, physical evidence, people, and process. The 7P concept is also very suitable if it is developed in the world of trading business. Anjani, Irham and Waluyati (2018) conducted a study on the formation of customer loyalty (the dependent variable) in the Traditional Market by using 7P as the independent variable. The results of their study found that managing 7P in traditional markets was able to increase buyer loyalty in traditional markets. Relevant to the research the writer will adopt, where the authors propose the 7P concept as a marketing strategy in increasing the number of tenants in Medan Focal Points.

As described above, if examined using the 7P approach, the first approach is the "Product" or features inherent in the Medan Focal Point, such as location, building layout, parking location, and so on. The results of the pre-study interview by the author conducted to several tenants stated that they were quite interested in the concept offered by Medan Focal Point in the form of a minimalist building appearance, not so big but packaged in a modern concept. Whereas the "Price" shows that Medan Focal Point offers quite competitive prices compared to Ringroad City Walk and Manhattan Times Square. Has been from the "Place" or in this case location. One of the reasons tenants choose Medan Focal Point is because it is in the middle of a promising location (between luxury housing and also a densely populated location) and easy to reach.

The concern of the tenants is the Medan Focal Point developers who are less intense in carrying out various promotional programs to the wider community, especially now that the conditions are not as crowded as in the early opening. Suggestions and input to carry out the promotion they continue to convey to the Medan Focal Point developers so that visitors are enthusiastic to come back and get back busy and make purchases at the available tenants.

The tenants also complained about the attitude of some Medan Focal Point management who seemed to lack response to their input. This they conveyed to the authors when the authors interviewed them at the time of pre-study. Same thing with the flow of the process in Medan Focal Point that the tenant feels is quite complicated.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategy

Strategy is the direction and scope of an organization in the long run that achieves profits for the organization through the configuration of resources in a challenging environment, to meet market needs and meet stakeholder expectations (Johnson and Scholes, 2016).

Marketing

Marketing is the process by which companies create value for customers and build strong relationships with customers, with the aim of capturing the value of customers in return (Kotler and Armstrong, 2014)

Marketing Strategy

The marketing strategy is a fundamental tool planned to reach the company by developing sustainable competitive advantage through the markets entered and marketing programs used to serve the target market (Tjiptono, 2012).

Market Penetration

Represents the market penetration strategy by identifying the market through

segmentation, targeting and mapping (Kotler and Armstrong, 2014).

Mall or Shopping Center

Malls or shopping centers are shopping centers that have one or several large department stores as an attraction for small retails with building typologies such as shops facing the pedestrian and also function as communal spaces for interaction between visitors and sellers (Savitri, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODS

Research is descriptive quantitative and associative. Research in associative descriptive problems is research that seeks to examine how a variable has an association or is related to other variables, or whether a variable is influenced by other variables (Juliandi, 2013).

This research will be conducted at Medan Focal Point. The time of the study will be conducted from October 2019 to December 2019. Where in this study the population studied was tenant consumers / tenants at the Medan Focal Point Mall, both those who have rented and who have been tenants with a total of 46 tenants. The method used in sampling uses a purposive sampling method, which is sampling that limits the specific characteristics of a person who provides the information needed by determining the correspondent who had been a renter in Medan Focal Point so that the number of samples in this study amounted to 32 tenant respondents.

The data used are Primary Data, i.e. the data used is through interviews with the mall directly with management representatives and to all tenants and Secondary Data, used is data in the form of company profiles and tenants from Medan Focal Point management.

Data collection techniques in the form of a questionnaire, which contains a list of questions related to the research variables will be distributed to each party of consumers who are expected to help in this study. Interviews, namely by way of asking questions directly to consumers who are

getting services at research sites and consumers who are not in place but have visited there and Observation, which is a direct observation on the object of research. Observations were made on the research object, namely Medan Focal Point in Medan.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main results in this study found that overall the marketing mix influenced the decision to use space for tenants in Medan Focal Points. As explained in the research problem that Medan Focal Point tenants feel dissatisfied with Medan Focal Point management because their expected turnover is not in line with expectations. The results of this study provide input for Medan Focal Point managers in their efforts to improve the decision to use space for tenants, especially for other tenant candidates.

The results of this study are in line with what was revealed by Tumbel and Rate (2015) in their research revealed that the marketing mix had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. They conduct research on traditional market customers in Manado City, where they base their research on this because of the increasingly widespread modern market in Manado City and to improve the purchasing decisions of traditional market customers, they conduct research from the marketing mix on purchasing decisions.

The results of subsequent studies conducted by Natakusumah and Yuliati (2016) where they found INA COOKIES customers in Bandung in making purchasing decisions were also influenced by the marketing mix conducted by INA COOKIES. The results of this study are in line with what the authors found in this study.

However, if seen partially, from 7 variables, there are 2 (two) variables that influence the decision to use space in the Focal Point, namely the variable "Promotion" (X4) and "Process" (X7). Where 5 (five) other variables do not have a

positive and significant effect. Pertiwi, Yulianto, Sunarti (2016) in their study of Baker's King Donuts & Coffee consumers at MX Mall Malang found that the marketing mix simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. However, partially, not all variables in the marketing mix affect purchasing decisions. They found that there were 3 (three) variables that influenced purchasing decisions, namely the "product", "promotion" and "place" variables, while the "product" variable did not influence the purchase decision.

Subsequent research was carried out by Wangarry, Tumbel and Karuntu (2018) where they found that simultaneously the marketing mix had an influence on purchasing decisions on PT. Hasjrat Abadi Ranotana, Makassar in buying a Honda motorcycle brand. However, only partially the "price" and "promotion" variables have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions, while the "product" and "place" variables have no effect.

Similar research was also produced by Fachriza and Moeliono (2017), where they found that simultaneously the marketing mix influenced purchasing decisions. However, they found 2 variables namely "product" and "place" which had a positive and significant effect, but the other 2 variables namely "price" and "promotion" had no influence on purchasing decisions.

Respondents' responses to Medan Focal Point based on this study were not satisfied. This can be seen from the average answers of the research respondents to the Marketing Mix questionnaire, where the average score of each variable as presented in Table 1 follows:

Table 1: Average Score of Questionnaire Variables

No	Variable	Average Score	Category
01	Products (X1)	3.26	Enough
02	Price (X2)	2.96	Not good
03	Location (X3)	2.89	Not good
04	Promotion (X4)	3.06	Enough
05	Physical Proof(X5)	2.33	Not good
06	People (X6)	3.09	Enough
07	Process (X7)	3.05	Enough

Source: Research Data Processing, 2020

Based on the average score above, it is clear that the majority of respondents are at an unsatisfactory level. This is a concern for the management of Focal Points, where their attitude is not satisfied if it is associated with the results of partial hypothesis testing only the variables "Promotion" and "Process" (X7) that affect the decision on the use of space for tenants in Medan Focal Point.

Managerial Implications

The results of the study revealed that the marketing mix had a positive and significant effect, so that this was an input for the management of Medan Focal Points. However, the research results partially found only 2 variables (out of a total of 7 variables) that significantly influenced the tenant's decision in choosing Medan Focal Point as their place of sales. The following managerial implications provide strategic advice to management in terms of 2 (two) variables, namely promotion and process variables.

For promotion, it can be directed by holding events such as educational exhibitions, for example the School & College Fair, Book Fair or presenting educational institutions as special tenants in the mall area that have a good name and are well known. Presenting other promotions such as travel fairs and travel education fairs with domestic and even foreign destinations that provide inspiration for travelers. And can bring tenant mall to three-star hotel class so that it can create attractive domestic travel packages. Inviting young creatives, influencers and celebrities in the world of music, culinary or other to hold interesting events by freeing up the cost of renting space in the atrium mall or empty space. or make up and photography creative classes which certainly provide education

For process variables, it can be innovated by presenting digital apps services for tenants and visitors which makes the flow of complaints, criticisms and suggestions more quickly information

for Medan Focal Point management. In this digital apps service also has the opportunity for tenants to promote their products directly to application users.

Promotion Aspects

The results showed the variable "Promotion" influenced the decision of tenants to choose Medan Focal Point as their place of sales. Promotional aspects are vital for tenants. At least this was obtained by researchers when researchers conducted observations and or interviews with tenants related to the results of this study. They stated that the Focal Point had not taken the promotion seriously. They have expressed their aspirations for Focal Point to hold certain events to attract visitors. However this has not been done by Medan Focal Point management.

When researchers conducted interviews with several visitors, they stated that they visited because there was a Starbuck, so this was an indication that Starbuck was carrying the good name of Medan Focal Point. This is a serious concern for the management of Medan Focal Point, lest visitors know the Starbuck outlet more than the Medan Focal Point itself.

Researchers also conducted interviews with other outlets that have big names in the city of Medan. They stated that one of their reluctance to choose the Medan Focal Point was because they considered the Medan Focal Point to be less known by the general public. Focal Points are like exclusive in marketing their names. This is an important concern for Medan Focal Point management, where they need to promote other tenants to avoid an exclusive impression

Process Aspects

In this study, it is also apparent that tenants consider management at Medan Focal Points to have an important concern in deciding whether they become tenants at Medan Focal Points or not. This can be seen from the existence of a positive and

significant relationship based on partial correlation. Medan Focal Point management needs to pay attention to aspects of management that are smooth, uncomplicated and the process of handling complaints quickly. This is a note of tenants when researchers conducted post-study interviews with tenants.

The tenants still consider the management of the Focal Point to be slow in responding, not listening to their input or aspirations. The obstacle they often face next is that management of the Focal Points often ignores the aspirations they convey, such as the procurement of events, inviting tenants who already have big names to boost the interest of the public to attend. As explained previously, the presence of Starbuck was able to become a magnet for Medan Focal Points.

Tenants also often face problems in the management's slow response in responding to complaints that they feel. These complaints can take days for them to get clarity from the management. This needs to be a concern for management. A process that makes it easy for tenants can increase tenants' confidence in trading at Medan Focal Point.

Parking in Medan Focal Point is also felt by consumers / narrow customers, so this is an input for Medan Focal Point management if they want to improve their existing processes.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion that has been done in this study, the researchers draw the following conclusions:

1. Simultaneously, there is a positive and significant effect of marketing mix with 7 variables on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point. This is indicated by the calculated F value is 30.291, greater than the F table score ($df_1 = 7; df_2 = 24; sig. = .05$) = 2.423, so H1-1 is accepted.

2. While partially only two variables namely "Promotion" and "Process" which have a positive and significant effect on the decision to use space at Focal Point, Medan. The details are as follows:

- a. The calculated value for Product (X1) is 0.066 < t_{table} , that is 2.069, this shows H1-2 is rejected, in other words the product does not have a positive and significant influence on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point.
- b. The calculated value for the price (X2) is 1.126 < t_{table} , that is 2.069, this shows H1-3 is rejected, in other words the price does not have a positive and significant effect on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point.
- c. The calculated value for place (X3) is 1.552 < t_{table} which is 2.069, this shows H1-4 is rejected, in other words place has no positive and significant influence on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point.
- d. The calculated value for promotion (X4) is 6.483 > t_{table} , that is 2.069, this shows H1-5 is accepted, in other words promotion has a positive and significant influence on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point.
- e. The calculated value for Physical Evidence (X5) is 0.124 < t_{table} , that is 2.069, this indicates H1-6 is rejected, in other words Physical Evidence does not have a positive and significant effect on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Points.
- f. The t_{count} for People (X6) is 0.710 < t_{table} , that is 2.069, this shows H1-7 is rejected, in other words People has no positive and significant influence on the decision to use space in Medan Focal Point.
- g. The calculated value for Process (X7) is 2.692 > t_{table} , that is 2.069, this indicates H1-8 is accepted, in other words the Process has a positive and significant effect on the

decision to use space in Medan Focal Points

Suggestion

Based on the results and discussion, there are a number of suggestions that can be made be delivered :

1. The results of this study find that simultaneous marketing mix influences purchasing decisions, but only partially physical evidence variables and processes that influence. This is a strategic input for Medan Focal Point managers to pay attention and focus on the management of their promotions and processes, including how managers organize events to increase public knowledge of Medan Focal Points and interact with tenants, listen to their aspirations and facilitate administration and so that tenants feel fulfilled what became their complaints.
2. This research explores the role of the marketing mix on space use decisions in Medan Focal Points, where purchasing decisions are not only influenced by the marketing mix, so it is advisable for further researchers to examine the role of other variables in influencing tenant use decisions, this is in addition to being beneficial for Medan managers Focal Point also adds scientific studies in the world of education, especially marketing management.

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